

After transfer, separate grafted kernels were placed on each of the following sterile substrates to germinate and grow: moist filter paper, moist sand, a perforated moist filter paper platform in a test tube, and a petri dish or test tube containing water agar (DIFCO) at concentrations of 2.0, 1.5, 1.0, 0.75, and 0.5%. In the water agar, grafted kernels were planted with the embryo end facing the cap or lid. Kernels were incubated at 26 + 2°C for 3 wk. Drops of SDW were added when necessary. For growth comparison, intact kernels of the two varieties

and their detached embryos were also placed in the media with the grafted kernels. To determine the best embryo age for successful grafting, embryos aged 4, 7, 10, and 14 d after anthesis were transferred to the mature endosperm of different varieties. Experiments were in four replications.

Grafting was confirmed when the endosperm was exhausted and squeezed into a thin membrane. After 2 wk, the embryo and the endosperm were completely bound together. Grafted plants were transferred to sterile pots with nutrient

solutions and covered with polyethylene sheets.

Results show that grafting was successful for BR4 and BR9 combinations (see table). The best substrate for grafted plant establishment was the 0.75% water agar medium. Grafting was successful only with embryos of more than 10 days after anthesis. Plants from grafted embryos and plants grown from normal seed were phenotypically similar in plant height, tiller number, and grain type. However, maturity date of grafted plants was 10-15 d later. □

Callus induction and plant regeneration from embryo tissues of rice

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We successfully induced calli and regenerated whole plantlets by culturing embryo-tissue of cultivar Palman 579, indicating that embryo culture might be used to propagate rice cultivars.

About 160 embryo tissues were cultured for callus induction; 80% began to grow as a separate friable mass of calli. Embryos were isolated from dehusked seeds, washed with distilled water, sterilized in 0.1% HgCl₂ solution for 10 min,

and washed 6 times in sterile distilled water. Embryos were cultured on Mura-shige and Skoog's medium (MS) (1962) supplemented by different concentrations of 2,4-D (1, 2, and 4 mg/liter). pH of the medium was adjusted to 5.8 and cultures were incubated at 26 ± 2°C with a 16 h/8 light/dark photoperiod. The MS medium was supplemented with 3% sucrose + 2,4-D (2 mg/liter) + coconut water (15% vol/vol) + casein hydrolysate (500 mg/liter).

After 34 subcultures, callus pieces were transferred to the differentiating medium containing MS + 1% sucrose + IAA (2 mg/liter) + coconut water (15 vol/vol) + casein hydrolysate (500 mg/liter). When

small shoot buds emerged on the surface of the callus tissues, 20% of the calli were separated into plantlets. Albino plants were occasionally found in the callus tissues.

Eighteen plantlets lived. They were transferred to MS basal medium with half the concentration of growth substances and then to a hormone-free basal medium to establish a vigorous root system. When plantlets grew 10-15 cm tall they were acclimatized in a growth chamber before transfer to the field. Albino plantlets died.

Meiotic analysis of the regenerated plants indicated a normal haploid chromosome number (n = 12). □

Pest management and control DISEASES

Control of black rot disease of azolla

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Black rot disease caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn is a serious disease of azolla. The pathogen first affects the middle portion of the azolla frond, then spreads gradually to the branches. Fronds rot and turn black in patches. We evaluated various fungicides for control of *R. solani* in in vitro laboratory tests. Carbendazim (2 - methoxy - carbamoyl benzimidazole) effectively inhibited *R. solani*. In a

later study, carbendazim was tested for *R. solani* control in 5-litre mud pots. Four litres of water, 5 ppm superphosphate, and 20 ppm carbofuran were added. Carbendazim levels of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 ppm were added to the pots. Azolla was inoculated at 15 g/pot. Azolla fresh weight was recorded 10 d later (see table).

When azolla was grown in mud pots, disease incidence substantially reduced azolla growth (see table). As carbendazim was increased, azolla growth also increased. Carbendazim at 50 ppm concentration gave maximum azolla growth.

Costs of using carbendazim are small (see table). A disease incidence is severe only in nursery plots where azolla growth

is abundant. Using the fungicides in nurseries may save azolla for field inoculation. □

Control of black rot disease of azolla, Tamil Nadu, India.

Carbendazim (ppm)	Mean azolla (g/pot)	% increase over control	Cost of carbendazim (\$/ha)
Control	8.33	—	—
10	16.67	100.12	0.19
20	19.00	128.09	0.38
30	19.17	130.13	0.57
40	19.83	138.06	0.75
50	20.67	148.14	0.94

CD: 1.0975